

INVESTIGATION OF STALL FLUTTER OF FAN BLADES BY BLADE TIP-TIMING SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Flutter is a system mode that all blades vibrate at the same frequency but with a different phase angle, which can form a nodal diameter (ND) pattern. One of the advantages of blade tip-timing (BTT) technique is to measure the vibrational displacements of all blades, which makes BTT a potential method to study flutter. This paper investigates the stall flutter of fan blades during an acceleration process through a BTT system with eight casing-mounted optical probes and one OPR (once per revolution) sensor. By applying the traveling wave plot, the non-integral vibration with three different frequencies is observed. Results indicate that it is a subsonic stall flutter at engine order (EO) 1.5 approximately with three nodal diameters (2, 3, 4) calculated by a cross-power spectral analysis based on the data of two probes. For all three nodal diameters, ND 2 is dominant. In comparison with Campbell diagram from modal analysis, EO1.5 crossing M1 is consistent with experimental results at around 92% design speed. As the rotor speed increases, the amplitudes of all blades experience a rapid growth at first. They then level off into a steady oscillating condition known as the limit amplitude region. Further increase in the rotor speed results in the growth of the blade amplitude into another limit amplitude region where the maximum blade displacement is nearly doubled. The development of nodal diameter as a function of rotor speed explains the formation of flutter. Furthermore, the change of phase difference between two blades shows a particular “rhombus” shape before flutter, which provides a new perspective to predict it.

INTRODUCTION

Flutter is always a problem need to be treated carefully during the development of gas turbine engines. Because the high-stress level caused by flutter can lead to blades failure, and the consequences are not affordable. Current designs pursue thinner blades and a higher pressure-ratio in one stage, which makes fan and compressor blades more easily to flutter [1]. Figure 1 shows a compressor performance map and explains different types of flutter encountered in a fan or compressor schematically. The most common flutter is stall flutter near the surge line that can be seen in fans and front compressor stages [2]. In particular, the flow has strong shocks in the blade passages in the case of supersonic stall flutter [3]. Supersonic unstall flutter can be observed in shrouded fans, which is not a practical design nowadays. This type of flutter tends to occur at climb conditions close to the maximum corrected speed [2]. Choke flutter is operating close to the choke line, and the flow is transonic over most of the blade chord [3]. This paper only focuses on the stall flutter with respect to fan blades.

Figure 1. One example of flutter compressor map

As a fluid/structure interaction instability problem, flutter has been studied for decades experimentally and numerically [4-11]. Those studies investigate the flow separates and viscous effects in the flow field or the relationship between aerodynamic damping and nodal diameter during flutter. In numerical analysis, the value of nodal diameter is often as a known parameter, which can be obtained by experiment. Therefore, flutter testing is a significant method in the design of turbomachinery. The strain gauge as the rotating frame sensor is a direct way to measure the strain on a local range in different directions, and it has been used for plenty of years. Nevertheless, it should be bonded to blade surface and a slip ring is needed for the data display in the stationary frame. These requirements make the test complicated and expensive, and only a few blades can be measured. In order to overcome the disadvantages of strain gauge sensors, blade tip-timing as a non-contact technique that is capable of measuring all blades in every revolution has been introduced.

The principle of BTT technique is based on the measurement of the blade arrival time. During vibration, the time of arrival of each blade is different compared with the reference value measured by an OPR sensor. The blade tip displacement can be calculated by multiplying this time difference with the blade tip speed and radius. For BTT system, there are three kinds of sensors can be selected, capacitive, eddy current and optical fibre sensors. Capacitive sensors are simple and inexpensive but they have a poor frequency response and require iron blades [12]. Eddy current sensors can be affected by the magnetic disturbance of the turbine engine and need to be calibrated in advance [13]. Optical fibre sensors have the advantages of the small laser spot, simple instrumentation, and high resolution [14]. Hence, optical sensors had been selected to detect flutter by monitoring the blade tip vibration. To verify mode shape analysis, Stargardter [15] used small blade-mounted mirrors that reflect laser light to capture the blade motion when blades are fluttering. Kurkov [16] resolved the problem that the torsional and bending contributions to the main flutter mode by using casing-mounted optical sensors. Watkins [17] built a near-real-time system for an engine fan stage with both strain gauge and optical sensors, and he found a flutter at 1.7EO with five different nodal diameters calculated by a cross-power analysis. Holzinger [18] investigated the influence of blade tip clearance on flutter in transonic compressors. Although these researchers have demonstrated that BTT technique with optical sensors can be an alternative way to study flutter, the blade individual behaviour concerning the nodal diameter pattern as a very prominent characteristic for flutter still remains elusive.

In the experiment, eight casing-mounted optical probes are used to measure the blade tip displacements of fan blades during an acceleration process. Three traditional methods have been applied to analyse the data: 1) one-probe method is able to identify the high response region and the blade vibrational frequency in stationary frame; 2) two-probe method is employed to calculate the nodal diameter; 3) Multi-probe method provides cross-checks for

the calculation of ND by using different combinations of two probes, and supports a sine curve fitting to extract the blade vibrational amplitude and phase. The additional data can help to understand blades behaviour better and offer a new way to predict flutter.

NOMENCLATURE

a_k	Coefficient of sinusoidal motion [-], $k=1, 2, 3$
A_n	The amplitude of nth nodal diameter [m]. $n \in \mathbb{N}$
d	Blade Displacement [m].
d_{ij}	Blade displacement of blade i measured by probe j [m], $i, j \in \mathbb{N}^+$
f_s	The frequency observed in the stationary reference frame [Hz].
F_s	The non-dimensional frequency observed in the stationary reference frame [-].
f_m	Sampling frequency [Hz].
m	The maximum nodal diameter [-].
n	The nth nodal diameter [-].
t	Physical time [s].
t_{ij}	The arrival time of blade i at probe j [s].
α_{ij}	The included angle between blade i and probe j [rad].
β	The angle between rotating and stationary reference frame at $t=0$.
γ_{ij}	Initial phase angle of blade i at probe j [rad].
θ_r	Angular position in the rotating frame [rad].
θ_0	Probe installation angle in the stationary reference frame [rad].
θ_j	Installation angle of Probe j [rad].
$\Delta\theta$	The circumferentially included angle between two probes [rad].
φ_x	Phase angle [rad], $x \in \mathbb{N}$
$\Delta\varphi$	The difference between the two-phase angles at the peak frequency [rad].
ω	Blade vibrational frequency [rad/s].
Ω	Rotor speed [rad/s].

DESCRIPTION OF EXPERIMENT

The test objective is to find out whether there is a large vibration in a certain speed range. A diagrammatic sketch of BTT testing system is presented in Fig.2. Due to the proprietary content, more details cannot be shown. For fan blades, the testing environment has a relative low pressure and temperature, which enables probes to work for a longer time. Eight optical probes have been mounted in the casing and located above the blade trailing edge. The circumferential position of each probe was determined based on the principle of minimum condition number in order to obtain a relative stable solution when applying the curve fitting method [19]. All probes are located in a plane perpendicular to shaft and connected with a laser unit. The laser wavelength is 625nm, and the spot size is about 1.5mm in diameter on blade surface when the tip clearance is 2mm. Each probe has two routes for laser transmitting and receiving, and it uses a minimum number of fibres allowing higher measurement resolutions to be obtained. There are individual channels built in the laser unit for receiving OPR signal. The OPR sensor is used to measure

the rotor speed through a metal object fixed to the shaft. All blades have been labelled a number against the rotation direction in order to facilitate the following analysis. The blade arrival time is recorded by the timing unit of which input bandwidth and timing resolution are 3MHz and 15ns respectively.

Figure 2. BTT set-up and the testing equipment

Figure 3 shows the change of rotor speed against revolution. As the speed increases with a growth rate $8.3r/s$ approximately, the increase of pressure ratio is faster than that of mass flow rate, which pushes the operating point to the surge line and leads to a large deflection detected in the red region. This strong vibration imposes restrictions on a further operation.

Figure 3. Rotor speed against revolutions

MODAL ANALYSIS

Modal analysis is a powerful tool that can identify the blade natural frequencies and the corresponding modal shapes. In structural vibration, the higher modes don't account for too much energy, which means they have little effect on the whole structure. Therefore, the first three modes of a single blade are calculated by ANSYS® under the pre-stressing force as a result of rotor speed. The aerodynamic load on the blade is neglected because it influences the frequency in a limited range [20]. In order to evaluate the performance of rotating blades, the Campbell diagram as a frequently used approach is introduced to describe the relationship between blade natural frequencies and external excitations (see Fig.4).

Figure 4. Campbell diagram

Campbell diagram consists of mode and engine order lines, which are straight passing through the origin and defined as the ratio of excitation frequency to rotor frequency. The integer EO represents the existing forces caused by static structures such as inlet guide vane or struts; however, non-integer EO is a result of flow instability referring to stall or flutter. The intersections of mode and EO lines indicate the possible resonance points.

RESULTS

1) One & two-probe method

Figure 5 shows the change of displacement of blade 6 measured by two probes, 1 and 5, from the 5000th to 5400th revolution. Blade vibrates on account of not only integral and non-integral excitations, but also noise caused by casing vibration or the optical sensor itself. In addition, the centrifugal force can lead to blade tip deformation, which is shown as the DC offset. Hence, after applying Savitzky-Golay smoothing, the integral component and blade steady offset are removed to a certain extent so that the non-integral part is presented more clearly. Both probes show a very similar trend. In the beginning, the response is quite small. At approximately 5100th revolution, the blade displacement starts to rise up and levels off into a limit amplitude region I afterwards, which refers to limit cycle oscillations (LCO). This is a classical response expected for an instability phenomenon (flutter) [1]. As the rotor speed increases further, blade 6 enters another limit amplitude region II with more violent vibration.

Figure 5. Raw data of blade 6 (up: probe 1; down: probe 5)

Considering the rotor blades as an ensemble and vibrate at a frequency $\omega/2\pi$, but different initial phase angles, which is able to form various nodal diameters. The vibration pattern in the rotating reference frame can be expressed as:

$$d = \sum_{n=-m}^m A_n e^{i(\omega t + n\theta_r)} \quad (1)$$

Where θ_r is angular position in rotating system, and m is the maximum nodal diameter, which is determined by the number of blades (NB). $m=NB/2$, if NB is even; otherwise, $m=(NB-1)/2$. A_n indicates the amplitude of n th nodal diameter. The coordinate transformation from rotating to stationary reference frame satisfies:

$$\theta_r = \theta_0 + \Omega t - \beta \quad (2)$$

Where θ_0 represents the probe installation position in stationary frame; Ω is the rotor speed, and β is the angle between rotating and stationary reference frame at $t=0$. Accordingly, substituting Eqn. (2) into (1) gives the expression of vibration pattern in stationary frame:

$$d = \sum_{n=-m}^m A_n e^{i((\omega+n\Omega)t+n\theta_0-n\beta)} \quad (3)$$

Therefore, the observed frequency by a signal probe is:

$$f_s = \frac{\omega + n\Omega}{2\pi} \quad (4)$$

Which is comprised of blade vibrational frequency and the frequency introduced by nodal diameter. Dividing both sides of the Eqn. (4) by $\Omega/2\pi$:

$$F_s = EO + ND \quad (5)$$

In order to determine ND, the cross-power spectral analysis is needed. The actual nodal diameter can be calculated by Eqn. (6).

$$ND = \frac{\varphi_2 - \varphi_1}{\theta_2 - \theta_1} = \frac{\Delta\varphi}{\Delta\theta} \quad (6)$$

Where $\Delta\varphi$ is the difference between the two-phase angles at the peak frequency; $\Delta\theta$ is the circumferentially included angle between two probes [17]. If ND is positive, the propagation direction of travelling wave is the same as

the rotation direction of fan blades and defined as forward travelling wave (FTW); otherwise, it belongs to the backward travelling wave (BTW).

According to the principle of BTT, the sampling frequency is equal to the number of blades multiplying rotor frequency. Base on Nyquist theorem, the maximum measured frequency should be:

$$f_m = \frac{\Omega \cdot NB}{4\pi} \quad (7)$$

Figure 6 displays the blade response throughout the experiment by creating a series of FFTs (Fast Fourier Transform). The abscissa axis represents the non-dimensional frequency, which is made up of engine order and nodal diameter; and ordinate axis is the FFT revolutions. Each FFT revolution contains the data from several revolutions to ensure there is enough data to perform FFT. There are a number of frequency components including integral and non-integral responses, and the most pronounced one has a non-integral value, 3.5.

Figure 6. Travelling wave plot

By applying Eqn. (6) to the three non-integral response, three different nodal diameters (2, 3, 4) corresponding to the forward travelling wave are obtained and ND2 is a dominant one. Hence, the blade vibrational frequency is one and a half times rotor frequency. From Campbell diagram, EO1.5 crossing M1 was found at around 92% design speed, which means this is a subsonic stall flutter with the 1st flex mode.

The whole process of nodal diameter variation with an interval of ten revolutions is shown in Fig. 7. In Each revolution, the nodal diameter is calculated only if the response surpasses 10% of the peak value. At first, the distribution of ND is broad, and both forward and backward travelling wave are existing. Since the blade vibrational energy depends on the magnitude of the vibration, the energy is very dispersed at this moment. Then the number of nodal diameters decreases slowly until only three of them are left, which are forward travelling wave. The energy is transferred from the BTW to the FTW unidirectionally. After that, the ND distribution expands again. From the development of nodal diameter, it can be concluded that the formation of flutter is a process of nodal diameter gathering and energy aggregation.

Figure 7. The development of nodal diameter calculated by probe 1 and 5

Moreover, it's worth mentioning that ND2 always exists despite the change in rotor speed. By monitoring the nodal diameter corresponding to the maximum response, it's also found that ND is fixed at 2 from the 5100th to 5350th FFT revolutions in Fig. 8.

Figure 8. Dominant nodal diameter in each revolution

2) Multi-probe method

The displacement of blade i at probe j can be calculated by:

$$d_{ij} = (t_{ij} - \frac{\alpha_{ij}}{\Omega}) \cdot \Omega \cdot r \quad (8)$$

Figure 9. A schematic diagram of blade tip-timing measurement

Assuming the blade vibration can be described by a sinusoidal motion (see Fig.9):

$$\begin{aligned} d_{ij} &= A \cdot \sin(\omega \cdot t_{ij} + \gamma_{ij}) \\ &= A \cdot \sin(\frac{\omega}{\Omega} \cdot \Omega \cdot t_{ij} + \gamma_{ij}) \\ &= A \cdot \sin(\text{EO} \cdot \theta_j + \tilde{\gamma}_{ij}) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Where γ_{ij} is the phase angle corresponding to the start of current revolution, and $\tilde{\gamma}_{ij}$ can be expressed by:

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\gamma}_{ij} &= \gamma_{ij} + (t_{ij} - \frac{\alpha_{ij}}{\Omega}) \cdot \omega + (\alpha_{ij} - \theta_j) \cdot EO \\ &= \gamma_{ij} + t_{ij} \cdot \omega - \theta_j \cdot EO\end{aligned}\quad (10)$$

Therefore, we can calculate the vibrational amplitude and phase based on Least Square Model in each revolution by the known parameters (see Fig.10).

$$d_{ij} = a_0 + a_1 \sin(EO \cdot \theta_j) + a_2 \cos(EO \cdot \theta_j) \quad (11)$$

$$\tilde{\gamma}_{ij} = \arccos\left(\frac{a_1}{\sqrt{a_1^2 + a_2^2}}\right) \quad (12)$$

Where a_0 , a_1 , a_2 are coefficients need to be calculated so as to obtain the blade vibrational amplitude and phase. The initial phase angle for blade i is:

$$\gamma_{ij} = \arccos\left(\frac{a_1}{\sqrt{a_1^2 + a_2^2}}\right) - t_{ij} \cdot \omega + \theta_j \cdot EO \quad (13)$$

Figure 10. Probes distribution example

Figure 11 exhibits the calculated peak-to-peak amplitude of all blades from the 4600th to 5400th revolution. It also shows two similar limit amplitude regions similar to the raw data measured by the individual probe. The second limit amplitude is almost twice as large as that of the first one.

Figure 11. Peak-to-peak amplitudes of all blades

The amplitude of each blade was coloured according to their magnitude of amplitude at the 5300th revolution in Fig. 12. Each blade is presented as a bright strip. Although

there is a little discrepancy due to the blade individual characteristics or different kinds of excitations, the nodal diameter pattern still can be observed directly and it's a combination of nodal diameter 2, 3, 4 primarily.

Figure 12. Nodal diameter pattern at the 5300th revolution

The phase change of blade 1 at probe 1 is presented in figure 13. Although the phase pattern is just in chaos at the very start, it suddenly presents some kind of regular variation after the 5120th revolution. The phase angle gradually decreases from 90° to -90° , and then shifts back to 90° approximately.

Figure 13. Variation trend of phase angle $\tilde{\gamma}_{11}$

Furthermore, taking all blades into account, the phase differences between blade i and blade 1 forms a “rhombus” through several revolutions (see Fig.14). This phenomenon indicates that all blades are locked in this situation despite of their individual difference. Note that the “rhombus” forms while the blade vibrational amplitude is still increasing. Accordingly, it can be defined as a precursor of flutter, and if this kind of variation can be captured, there is a chance to predict flutter and protect blades. From the next enlarged figure, the phase shift of each blade was also observed, which represents blade vibrating at its natural frequency. This result is in accordance with the previous analysis.

Figure 14. Phase difference between blade i and blade 1 (Phase2-1: Phase difference between blade2 and blade1)

CONCLUSIONS

This paper studies the phenomenon of subsonic stall flutter of fan blades by the blade tip-timing technique during an acceleration process. Owing to the advantage of all-blade measurement, BTT is able to realize the observation of nodal diameter directly and provide more information in relation to the blade vibration. The significant conclusions can be drawn as:

With the development of nodal diameter, the formation of flutter can be regarded as a process of nodal diameter gathering and energy aggregation. In addition, it's possible that more than one nodal diameter appears during flutter. Therefore, the numerical simulation should take this situation into account to get more precise results.

The particular "rhombus" shape established by phase differences in several revolutions implies that all blades are interconnected, and it forms in advance of the limit cycle oscillation, which can be considered the precursor of flutter. Namely, this is a potential method to predict flutter for turbomachinery.

When the rotor speed keeps increasing, fan blades can enter another limit amplitude region where the peak amplitude almost doubles compared with that of the previous limit amplitude region.

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